

Barriers to Covid-19 Vaccine Acceptance Among Health Workers

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Abstract:

COVID-19 (the popular name for the Coronavirus Disease 2019), is a disease of the respiratory system caused by the Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome, Corona Virus-2 (SARS-CoV-2), and it was declared a pandemic by the World Health Organization on the 11th of March, 2020. Frantic efforts have been put in place by the local, state and federal government to curb the spread and effect of covid-19 pandemic with the use of vaccines. Rather than being celebrated, the eventual discovery of systems of vaccination against COVID-19 pandemic was otherwise greeted with pessimism, causing attrition and low uptake of the vaccines in some cultures, especially in African countries. The disease kept on spreading and causing havoc. Despite having a number of COVID-19 vaccines available and approved for public use, the uptake appears to be low. Some of the reasons for this low uptake may include level of trust in the healthcare system, educational background, presence of conspiracy theories, social, traditional and religious beliefs, social media, fear of adverse side effects, personal risk perception. This paper recommends that the government should create more awareness about COVID-19 vaccination and make available the trials which the vaccines had gone through to health workers so as to convince them on the acceptance of the vaccines.

Keywords: Acceptance, Barriers, COVID-19, Health Workers Vaccine,

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Introduction

The COVID-19 is the fifth reported pandemic in history since the 1918 Spanish flu, which is also known as the 1918 influenza pandemic (Liu *et al.*, 2020). The Spanish flu was caused by the H1N1 Influenza A Virus between February 1918 and April 1920. In four successive waves, about 500 million people (about 33% of the world's population at that time) were affected. There was a second wave of COVID-19 worldwide, despite all the efforts and preventive measures put in by the affected Nations of the world (Allagoa *et al.*, 2021). The third wave is presently ongoing in France, Spain and Germany. The strain of the COVID-19 in India appears to be more virulent as it has been associated with more morbidity and mortality. The prevalence of COVID-19 in Nigeria is 12.2%, with a recovery rate of 82%, and a case fatality rate of 1.2%. To prevent a similar death toll of the 1918 flu, the world population will have to be vaccinated against COVID-19 (Amaze *et al.*, 2021).

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Corona viruses are zoonotic i.e. the first develop in animal before being transmitted to humans. A person has to come into close contact with an animal that has the infection. Once it develops in people it can be transmitted from person to person through respiratory droplets. The viral material hangs out in droplets and can be breathed into the respiratory tract (windpipe and lungs) where the virus can then lead to an infection. Man can also acquire SARS-COV-2 by touching the mouth nose or eyes after touching a surface or object that has the virus.

To test for the COVID-19 virus, a health care provider takes a sample from the nose (nasopharyngeal swab), throat (throat swab) or saliva. The samples are then sent to a laboratory for testing. If an individual is coughing up sputum, such can be sent for testing. The FDA has authorized at-home tests for the COVID-19 virus. These are available only with a doctor's prescription (WHO, 2022)

Overview of COVID-19 Vaccination

With everything slowing down or coming to a halt, scientists and health practitioners have delved into trying to find a permanent solution so that life can go back to its normal. Multi-agency efforts on research have been facilitated in pursuit of developing vaccines for immunization to prevent COVID-19 infection. These vaccines have different working mechanisms to protect individuals against the disease (Terefa, et al., 2021).

The research on finding a vaccine and improved detection for the disease have moved at an unprecedented pace for reasons such as advancement in research, increased innovative vaccine technology equipment, the human trial was done at an early stage, and lastly great unity between relevant bodies. There are various vaccines developed to protect people from the transmission and adverse effects of the virus. Preliminary data shows support for this statement as countries are reporting a decrease in the transmission rate (Mahmud, et al., 2021).

For instance, Israel claims to have vaccinated almost 75% of its older population, an action that has seen a 33% decrease in the transmission rate of the virus. That notwithstanding, the impact of COVID-19 vaccines on the transmission of the disease has not yet been fully

determined. The Strategic Advisory Group of Experts (SAGE), through evidence-based medicine, gives temporary guidance on issues to do with immunization. Priority is given to health workers and people aged above 65 years because vaccines are limited and they also face a higher risk of getting infected.

Researchers across the world have been working assiduously to develop vaccines against the highly contagious virus. Approximately Sixty (60) COVID-19 vaccines candidates are undergoing clinical evaluations, and another one hundred and seventy-two (172) COVID-19 candidate vaccines are at the preclinical evaluation stage as of December 29, 2020. It is believed that some of these vaccines will be ready for use by early 2021. However, there are widespread skepticism and divergent views regarding the legitimacy of various COVID-19 vaccines among people across the globe. The effectiveness of vaccination programs and the global objective of eradicating the pandemic require optimal acceptance of the vaccine across all countries. The success of any vaccination program is largely dependent on how well the vaccines are accepted among the population and the willingness of people to be vaccinated (WHO, 2022).

Vaccination is an effective way of combating infectious conditions. As of 26th March 2021, 83 vaccines were in the clinical development stage while 184 were at the pre-clinical development stage. Globally, several vaccines have been deemed safe and effective for human use, including Pfizer, Oxford/AstraZeneca, Moderna, Janssen, Sputnik V, Sinovac, and Sinopharm. Due to the inadequate supply of COVID-19 vaccines globally, governments have prioritized high-risk groups to receive the initial supply of vaccines (WHO, 2022).

The availability of COVID-19 vaccines may not translate into its uptake. Although governments will provide the vaccines, their uptake is voluntary. Indeed, several studies have demonstrated that not all health care workers are ready to accept COVID-19 vaccines when made available in their country. For example, a study conducted in the Democratic Republic of Congo found that approximately 28% of health care workers were willing to receive the COVID-19 vaccine if available (Elkalmi, et al., 2021).

In response to the massive global effects of COVID-19, multiple laboratories worldwide are working to create an effective vaccine. The possibility that one will be available in 12 to 18 months is seen by many as the most promising means of controlling the COVID-19 pandemic. Over the past century, vaccinations have become a routine and effective preventive measure in reducing the rate of and eradicating or nearly eradicating certain viral illnesses. Besides providing direct immunity and preventing disease among vaccinated individuals, vaccines have been shown to reduce infections even among individuals who are not vaccinated, through herd immunity, if a sufficient proportion of the population is immune. Many pharmaceutical companies and research laboratories are currently working with messenger RNA, DNA, subunit, virus-like particles and viral vectors to discover an effective vaccine for the COVID-19 pandemic. On an unprecedented timeline, multiple vaccines have been developed and are currently being tested in large-scale phase 3 trials, suggesting that a vaccine may be available in the foreseeable future. The great potential of a vaccine against COVID-19 is tempered by rising vaccine skepticism in the United States and worldwide, which may present challenges to widespread vaccine uptake when a vaccine becomes available (Terefa, et al., 2021).

Available COVID-19 Vaccines

Some vaccines are presently available, and approved for public use. These vaccines include Oxford/AstraZeneca viral vector vaccine, Pfizer/BioNTech mRNA vaccine, Moderna RNA vaccine, Janssen/Johnson and Johnson viral vector vaccine, Sinopharm inactivated viral vaccine, Sinovac inactivated viral vaccine, Gamaleya viral vector vaccine, Bharat Biotech Inactivated viral vaccine (Covaxin) and Novavax Protein subunit vaccine (GAVI, 2021). To fight COVID-19, affordable vaccines need to be developed, and distributed across the world, and every individual needs to be vaccinated. According to the World Health Organisation, “no one is safe until everyone is safe.” For this reason, COVAX was launched in 2020. Previously known as COVID-19 Vaccines Global Access Facility, COVAX is a worldwide initiative with the main objective to develop, manufacture and distribute COVID-19 vaccines fairly and evenly around the world (Terefa, et al., 2021, Adedeji-Ademola, et al., 2022, Mahmud, et al., 2021). COVAX is coordinated by the World Health Organization in collaboration with the Vaccine Alliance (Gavi) and the Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness Innovations (CEPI). In April 2020, ACT Accelerator was launched in partnership with the European Commission and France to fight the COVID-19 pandemic. Apart from enhancing the production and worldwide distribution of the COVID-19 vaccines, COVAX funds the access to the COVID-19 vaccines for under-developed countries, thereby bridging the gap between the developed and under-developed Nations of the world.

The plan of COVAX is to provide two billion doses of various vaccines to 190 countries in the year 2021, ensuring vaccination of up to 20 percent of the world’s population. The most important objective of COVAX is to send vaccines to 92 less-wealthy countries free-of-charge. Nigeria is one of these less-wealthy countries.

The Oxford–AstraZeneca COVID-19 vaccine, codenamed AZD1222, and sold under the brand names Covishield and Vaxzevria among others, is a viral vector vaccine for prevention of COVID-19. Developed by Oxford University and AstraZeneca, it is given by intramuscular injection, using as a vector the modified chimpanzee adenovirus ChAdOx1. Studies carried out in 2020 showed that the efficacy of the vaccine is 76.0% at preventing symptomatic COVID-19 beginning at 22 days following the first dose and 81.3% after the second dose. Another analysis showed that, for symptomatic COVID-19 infection after the second dose, the vaccine is 66% effective against the Alpha variant (lineage B.1.1.7), and 60% against the Delta variant (lineage B.1.617.2) (Alhassan, et al., 2021).

As of April 2021, WHO reported that 102 countries in six continents have received almost 38.4 million doses of COVID-19 vaccines through the COVAX facility, Nigeria received 3,924,000 doses of the Oxford/AstraZeneca COVID-19 vaccine through COVAX on March 2, 2021. Vaccination commenced at the Federal Medical Centre, Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria on March 15, 2021. However, the turnout of hospital staff was low, necessitating extension of vaccination by three weeks. Therefore, this study was undertaken to access the reasons behind the low turnout of health workers for COVID-19 vaccination.

This vaccine works based on the virus’s genetic instructions for building the spike protein. But unlike the Pfizer-BioNTech and Moderna vaccines, which store the instructions in single-stranded RNA, the Oxford vaccine uses double-stranded DNA. Adenoviruses are common viruses that typically cause colds or flu-like symptoms. The Oxford-AstraZeneca team use a

modified version of a chimpanzee adenovirus, known as ChAdOx1. It can penetrate cells, but it cannot replicate inside them (Fowlkes, et al., 2021).

The Oxford-AstraZeneca vaccine for Covid-19 is more rugged than the mRNA vaccines from other companies. DNA is not as fragile as RNA, and the adenovirus's tough protein coat helps protect the genetic material inside. As a result, the Oxford vaccine does not have to stay frozen. The vaccine is expected to last for at least six months when refrigerated at 38–46°F (2–8°C) (The New York Times, 2021).

After the vaccine is injected into a person's arm, the adenoviruses bump into cells and latch onto proteins on their surface. The cell engulfs the virus in a bubble and pulls it inside. Once inside, the adenovirus escapes from the bubble and travels to the nucleus, the chamber where the cell's DNA is stored. The adenovirus pushes its DNA into the nucleus. The adenovirus is engineered so it cannot make copies of itself, but the gene for the coronavirus spike protein can be read by the cell and copied into a molecule called messenger RNA, or mRNA. The mRNA leaves the nucleus, and the cell's molecules read its sequence and begin assembling spike proteins (The New York Times, 2021).

Pfizer has an active ingredient mod RNA that encodes the spike of SARS-Cov-2, the lipid hexane-6,1-diyl and salts such as potassium chloride, potassium phosphate and finally sucrose. Thirty-nine cases in BNT162b2 group and eighty-two (82) cases in placebo group were observed between the first and second doses. The vaccine efficacy was determined at 52% and 95 confidence intervals. Early protection was noticed from as early as 12 days after the first dose. Local and systemic reactions and use of medication was tested using data collected from 8,183 participants for 7 days after vaccination (El-Elimat, et al., 2021).

Pain at injection site was assessed basing on severity. Redness and swelling were also measured based on severity. Additional scales of measurement were fatigue, headache, chills, muscle and joint pain, vomiting and diarrhoea. Under local reactions, pain at the injection site was a key feature affecting both the below and above 55-year-olds irrespective of the dosage in those with BNT162b2. The participants in the placebo group however felt less pain at the injection site. Irrespective of age or type of dosage, in systemic reactions, fatigue was highest and vomiting lowest. Those with BNT162b2 had higher rates than those with placebo.

An observational study from Israel shows that Pfizer is 26% effective at preventing infection on people who have not been infected before, which is then boosted to 92% by the second shot. The vaccine is administered through an injection on the upper arm, and to be given to people above 16 years. Those with severe allergic reactions to any ingredient used in the manufacture of the vaccine or may experience an allergy after the first shot are advised not to take the vaccine. Clinical trials showed mild or moderate side effect that occurs within 7 days after getting the shot, with only a few getting severe side effects to the point of hospitalization or death. These include tiredness, swelling, muscle pain, nausea, etc (Terefa, et al., 2021).

Benefits of Receiving the Vaccine

Millions of people around the world have received COVID-19 vaccines since they were authorized for emergency use by FDA. COVID-19 vaccines have undergone and will continue to undergo the most intensive safety monitoring in the world history. Learn more about how federal partners are continuing to closely monitor vaccine safety. A growing body of evidence has shown that these vaccines are safe and effective. COVID-19 vaccines were developed using scientific methods that have been around for decades. Before recommending COVID-19

vaccination, scientists conducted clinical trials. The FDA gave the Pfizer BioNTech COVID-19 vaccine emergency authorization to use in children ages 5 years through 15 years and full approval to use in people ages 16 years and older (Terefa, et al., 2021).

Some people have no side effects from COVID-19 vaccines while people have reported side effects that may affect their ability to do daily activities, but they could go away within a few days. Also, there is no evidence that COVID-19 vaccines cause fertility problems as the benefits of COVID-19 vaccination outweigh the known and potential risks. Reports of adverse events, like allergic reactions or myocarditis or pericarditis, are also rare. For the avoidance of doubt, everyone who receives a COVID-19 vaccine can participate in safety monitoring by enrolling themselves and their children ages 5 years and older in v-safe and completing health check-ins after COVID-19 vaccination (Mahmud, et al., 2021).

COVID -19-vaccines are effective and can reduce the risk of getting and spreading the virus that causes COVID-19 as they help children and adults from getting seriously ill even if they do get COVID-19. Though COVID-19 tends to be milder in children than adults, it can make children very sick, require hospitalization, and some children have even died. Children with underlying medical conditions are more at risk for severe illness compared to children without underlying medical conditions. Getting children ages 5 years and older vaccinated can help protect them from serious short- and long-term complications, the same way everyone from age 5 years and older who get vaccinated receives protection for their families and communities, including friends and family who are not eligible for vaccination and people at increased risk for severe illness from COVID-19 (WHO, 2022).

In a related sense, after children and adults are fully vaccinated for COVID-19, they can resume many activities that they did before the pandemic. CDC recommends that fully vaccinated people wear a mask in public or indoor settings if they are in an area of substantial or high transmission. Fully vaccinated people might choose to mask regardless of the level of transmission, particularly if they or someone in their household is immune-compromised or at increased risk for severe disease, or if someone in their household is unvaccinated (Kalam, et al., 2021).

Additionally, children ages 5 years and older and adults who are eligible should get vaccinated regardless of whether they already had COVID-19. Evidence is emerging that people get better protection by being fully vaccinated compared with previously having a COVID-19 infection. One study showed that unvaccinated people who already had COVID-19 are more than two times more likely than fully vaccinated people to get COVID-19 again. This implies that immunity may only come after COVID-19 vaccination as none of the COVID-19 vaccines gives people COVID-19 because none of the COVID-19 vaccines contain the live virus that causes COVID-19, so COVID-19 vaccines cannot make anyone sick with COVID-19.

Finally, vaccines continue to reduce a person's risk of contracting the virus that causes COVID-19, including the different variants. Vaccines continue to be highly effective at preventing hospitalization and death, including against this variant. Fully vaccinated people with breakthrough infections from this variant only appear to be infectious but for a shorter period.

Acceptance Level of the Uptake of COVID-19 Vaccination

Hence, gaining an understanding of the resources that people trust the most to get information about COVID-19 vaccines is critical for the success of any future national vaccination campaign. In a further study, COVID-19 vaccine acceptance among college students in South Carolina was found to be affected by the information resources. Students largely trusted scientists (83), followed by healthcare providers (74), and then health agencies (70) (Qiao et al in Kalam, et al., 2021). In a study from France, vaccination practices and acceptance toward MMR and HBV vaccines were better when parents had reported getting the information from their healthcare providers compared with parents getting information from the internet or their relatives (Adedeji-Ademola, et al., 2020).

Recent research from China indicates that engaging in hand hygiene and other health protective behaviors was associated with reduced psychological impact of the COVID-19 outbreak, including lower stress and anxiety (El-Elimat., et al., 2021). These findings highlight the importance of encouraging the public to engage with such behaviors not only to reduce the risk of infection but also to reduce anxiety associated with COVID19. Over the past decade, it has comprehensively explored the landscape of vaccine confidence issues and experiences in managing confidence crises around the world (Fowlkes, et al., 2021). These studies have focused that a multiplicity of factors influencing vaccine decisions, key drivers of public confidence in vaccines were identified as trust in the importance, safety, and effectiveness of vaccines, along with compatibility of vaccination with religious beliefs (Alhassan, et al., 2021). These findings have resulted in the development of a Vaccine Confidence Index survey tool to measure individual perceptions on the safety, importance, effectiveness, and religious compatibility of vaccines. The research questionnaire has the primary focus of measuring confidence across multiple countries while being minimal, thus allowing ready integration into existing global surveys.

The survey is one of a diverse set of metrics and indices used to measure confidence or hesitancy such as the Parent Attitudes About Childhood Vaccines Survey, which measures vaccine hesitancy among parents; the Vaccination Confidence Scale, which measures confidence in adolescent vaccination; the 5-C scale such as confidence, complacency, constraints, calculation, and collective responsibility, which identifies psychological barriers of vaccination behavior; and the SAGE Vaccine Hesitancy Scale, which has been deployed across multiple countries (Elkalmi, et al., 2021).

In 2017, the vaccine manufacturer Sanofi announced that their newly introduced dengue vaccine Dengvaxia posed a risk to individuals who had not previously been exposed to the virus, prompting outrage and panic across the population where nearly 850 000 children had been given the new vaccine the previous year. As the research measured a baseline confidence value in 2015, that were able to measure the change in confidence following the vaccine scare and found a significant drop in confidence in vaccine importance, safety, effectiveness (Larson et al 2019).

The survey study tool has detected a rise in confidence across the country although confidence is not back to 2015 levels indicating a possible recovery and highlighting the value of the tool in assessing the effectiveness of national level policy. Japan ranked among the countries with the lowest vaccine confidence in the world: this might be linked to the human

papillomavirus (HPV) vaccine safety scares that started in 2013, and following the decision by the Japanese Ministry of Health, Labor and Welfare in June, 2013, to suspend proactive recommendation of the HPV vaccine (Simms et al 2020).

As a result of this vaccine safety scare, HPV vaccination coverage decreased from 68.4–74.0 in the 1994–98 birth cohort to 0•6 in the 2000 birth cohort.³⁶ The news of Japan suspending their proactive recommendation of the HPV vaccine has travelled globally through online media and social media networks, being applauded by ant vaccination groups but not by the global scientific community (Larson et al 2014). Moreover, Indonesia witnessed a large drop in confidence between 2015 and 2019, partly triggered by Muslim leaders questioning the safety of the measles, mumps, and rubella (MMR) vaccine, and ultimately issuing a religious ruling claiming that the vaccine was haram and contained ingredients derived from pigs and thus not acceptable for Muslims.

These relationships may be complicated for example, an individual highly compliant with social distancing measures may perceive their risk to be low but still want to obtain a vaccine. Lower vaccine acceptance among the retired population might be influenced by lower perceived risk. Although the elderly are more vulnerable to COVID-19, most of the retired population in Southeast Asian countries have low mobility and spend more time at home with less travel. These behaviors may lead them to having a lower perceived risk of being infected with SARS-CoV-2, and eventually may lead to lower acceptance of a vaccine. Moreover, their acceptance might also be influenced by knowledge about the disease. Much of the information about COVID-19 is spread through social media or online media, which is less frequently accessed by older adults. Therefore, older adults might have less exposure to information about COVID-19 that could contribute to framing their risk perception. In addition, less social media use might also be associated with less knowledge among the elderly and this could affect their perceived risk and vaccine acceptance (Terefa, et al., 2021).

Barriers to Acceptance of the Vaccine

Apart from religious and cultural reasons or health conditions that justify not receiving the vaccine, the choice to refuse vaccination can be explained by a range of other factors. The following nine factors provide a good picture of the complexity of the situation (Terefa, et al., 2021, Mahmud, et al., 2021, Fowlkes, et al., 2021).

Misunderstanding and Lack of Information

A first barrier is lack of understanding about the vaccine or misunderstanding the necessity of vaccination. Faced with contradictory opinions and lack of information, some people are perplexed: Why should you get vaccinated if you can still catch the virus and transmit it? Why vaccinate young people if they are less vulnerable to the virus? Not finding satisfactory answers to these questions can paralyze someone's thought and reduce their willingness to take action.

Fear of Needles and Vaccines

Some people have a strong fear of needles or the pain related to vaccination. Although this fear may seem irrational to others, it is something the sufferer feels intensely, apprehension about needles or pain is sometimes so anxiety-producing that it can lead a person to avoid any situation that involves vaccination. Sometimes just seeing images of vaccination can

provoke anxiety. In other cases, the fear is related to the possible side effects of the vaccine. Some people may not refuse to be vaccinated, but will wait until more people have been vaccinated so they can see if there are any long-term side effects (Terefa, et al., 2022)).

Feelings of Helplessness

A further psychological barrier comes from the feelings of helplessness and discouragement in response to the possibility that the pandemic will continue, despite vaccination efforts, especially given the detection of new variants. The term “pandemic fatigue” reflects the weary and demotivated feeling that arises during a time of crisis when events appear to repeat themselves. Resignation and loss of hope can lead to reduced motivation, and unwillingness to follow recommendations, including vaccination.

Lackadaisical Attitude (Aware but Not Concerned)

Other people are aware of the impact of the pandemic, but do not feel personally concerned: “I’m healthy, so that protects me.” These individuals often lack knowledge about the disease and vaccination, so they are not particularly concerned about the harmful effects of the virus on their health or the risks of transmission to others. It is worthy to note that these people are not actually opposed to the vaccine (Mahmud, et al., 2021).

Mistrust of Ingredients

Some people pay close attention to what goes into their bodies and may be concerned about the ingredients of the COVID-19 vaccine. They experience visceral discomfort at the idea of getting a vaccination, and may perceive the COVID-19 vaccine as an intrusion, contamination or aggression. Not knowing about the ingredients of the vaccine, they may be reluctant or even opposed to receiving it (Terefa, et al., 2021; Mayo Clinic, 2021).

Anxiety and Denial

Everyone reacts differently to anxiety-provoking situations. Some will jump into action and look for solutions; others will confide in loved ones or feel emotionally overwhelmed. Still others will go into denial. Denial is an automatic, unconscious reflex that works as a Band-Aid to control anxiety. In the pandemic context, this may be expressed as denial of the seriousness of the disease, denial of one’s own vulnerability to contracting the virus, or even denial of the existence of the virus itself (Olomofe, et al., 2021).

Sense of Rejection and Exclusion

As social beings, we are extremely sensitive to rejection. Rejection may be more common and painful for some than for others. These people feel more excluded from society and do not recognize themselves in the official discourse or the norms being proposed in response to the pandemic. When health measures are announced, these people may find them controlling. When one feels neither represented nor listened to by the authorities, or when one is parodied or criticized by other groups in society, the wounds of a past marked by rejection are reactivated and replayed. These people will also feel excluded and less likely to follow recommendations. They are also more likely to feel better understood by alternative and refractory voices that make them feel heard at last (Terefa, et al., 2021).

Dependency and Conflict Avoidance

Some people are more dependent on the opinions of those closest to them. The dynamics of the relationship are such that the person doubts themselves, relies on the other person to make day-to-day decisions for them and idealizes the other person or seeks to minimize

conflicts with them. In these cases, the person's position and choice will be influenced by the fact that their peer does not consider vaccination to be important (Malik, et al., 2021).

Crisis of Confidence

The previously mentioned factors, such as mistrust of what goes into the body, denial and rejection, may crystallize into a greater distrust of government sources, health authorities and the pharmaceutical industry. This can also turn into crisis of confidence and distrust of public health recommendations. belief in conspiracy theories and the rejection of authority can shape one's thinking and identity. That in turn creates a danger of polarization (Terefa, et al., 2021).

Conclusion

The major barrier to COVID-19 vaccine acceptance among health worker is due to incognizant COVID-19 vaccine. Barriers to COVID-19 vaccine acceptance among health workers is due to reasons such as: it is unsafe, lack of trust in government and manufacturers of the vaccine, that the vaccine has not gone through enough clinical trials, it could be associated with side effects, and lastly because they wanted to see what would happen to those who received the vaccine.

Government should do more to encourage health workers and the general public on receiving the vaccine through the social media. Every health worker should get the COVID-19 Vaccine as the reasons for hesitancy are not strong enough when compared to the fatality recorded so far. Emphasis should be stressed on the short life- span of the side effects following the vaccine jabs. Significant number of persons who have been vaccinated are living healthy lives as can be testified around us today, which as negated one of the reasons for hesitance.

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